

Terminology quality Checklist for medical terminology developers and evaluators

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Abstract

Background: Standardised terminology enables healthcare professionals to collaborate effectively. Digitised terminology, supported by terminology services, has become particularly important for semantic interoperability and data exchange. However, creating and maintaining terminology can be demanding and time-consuming. Cimino proposed essential criteria for medical terminologies to support modern computer applications. Over time, various healthcare-related terminologies have been developed, often diverging from these criteria and varying in quality.

Objectives: This research aims to design a methodology for **terminology quality assurance**. This methodology is intended to be applied to a terminology server, thereby facilitating the tasks of terminologists. With this methodology, we aim to automate quality rules within the terminology server software and manage ever-evolving digital terminologies.

Results: We propose a new methodology called **Checklist** for terminology quality assurance. The main idea is to guide terminologists in developing new terminology using quality rules based on the work of experts. Each rule contains acceptance criteria, enabling automatic validation within the terminology server.

Conclusions: Checklist empowers terminologists to design and support terminology that can gracefully evolve over time, reducing the maintenance costs associated with supporting terminology changes and modernisation.

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Checklist was applied to the TermX terminology server and verified in the Estonian Health and Welfare Information Systems Centre.

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1. Introduction

According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), terminology is a set of concepts and designations belonging to one domain or subject [1]. Maintainers of terminology recognise that terminologies are not fixed and static but evolve over time [2, 3].

Over time, various healthcare-related terminology has been developed for different purposes, including those intended to collect statistics or accounting information from healthcare institutions [4]. ICD-10 is used for public health surveillance. A list of healthcare services¹ has been issued by the Estonian Health Insurance Fund for the purpose of financial accounting and budgeting [5]. SNOMED CT is a comprehensive clinical terminology that provides a standardised way of representing clinical information in independent clinical information systems to support interoperability and information exchange between these systems[6, 4].

Some terminologies are based on ontologies, such as ICD-10, SNOMED CT, or LOINC, while others implement straightforward lists of codes and their textual meanings [7]. While ontology-based terminologies typically have well-defined, established development procedures, including quality assurance, other terminologies often do not follow even the basic principles of terminology development [8].

If terminology developers do not use terminology design principles, models, and standards, they may create inconsistent and controversial terminology or terminology unsuitable for machine processing [9]. As a result, various collaborators may interpret terminology differently, leading to inconsistency and semantic heterogeneity in the use of terminology.

Our objective is to devise a methodology for quality assurance in terminology. This methodology is intended to enhance the validation process of terminology developed within the TermX terminology server

¹<https://www.tervisekassa.ee/partnerile/raviasutusele/tervishoiuteenuste-loetelu>

(Table 1) utilising quality rules. It aims to guide the developer’s focus towards the principles of terminology design, as established by experts or necessitated by interoperability standards. Ultimately, this should contribute to the creation of consistent and cohesive terminology. Checklist is the main artefact we developed for the terminology validation process. Checklist is a methodology that includes a list of rules and formal acceptance criteria to be followed in the production of well-defined terminology that supports the evolution of terminology over time.

Table 1: Vocabulary

Term	Description
Terminology services	refer to a set of functionalities or tools that manage and manipulate terminologies, allow the semantic interoperability of them, and provide standardised programmatic access to them within a system or across systems [4, 10].
Terminology server	is a software component or system that hosts and manages terminologies. It is a specialised server that provides access to terminologies and often includes terminology services [4].
TermX	is a knowledge management and sharing platform, including a terminology server, a thesaurus, model designers, FML transformations, and authoring and publishing tools [11, 12].

The rest of the paper has been structured as follows. In Chapter 2, we formulate the problem and present the research method used. Chapter 3 outlines the paper’s main contribution: the Checklist methodology for evaluating terminology systems. We evaluate the proposed Checklist in Chapter 4 and conclude in Chapter 5.

2. Method

The terminologies require constant revision and evaluation; they evolve over time [13]. Individuals or small teams are not able to manage and operate the development and modification of large terminologies and therefore need tools to support efficient management and terminology work [14]. Software applications acquire knowledge from experts [15, 16, 17], but how do these tools support the quality of the developed terminologies? How can we define and apply the validation rules and quality criteria for terminology to software applications?

The basis of modern terminology theory emerged in 1930 with the work of Eugen Wüster [18]. Wüster developed a theory of terms and concepts that later became entrenched as the terminology standard promulgated by ISO [1, 19]. However, Wüster’s standard was developed for terminologies

used by humans; it does not meet the requirements placed on standardised terminologies in the era of the computer [8]. In 1998, James Cimino introduced a set of desiderata that must be satisfied by medical terminologies for them to support modern computer applications [20, 8]. The principles stated in Cimino’s desiderata are still the main criteria used to assess the consistency of clinical terminology today. Cimino’s desiderata have been thoroughly incorporated in the development of terminologies such as SNOMED CT [21], UMLS [22], and NHS Clinical Terms [23]. We selected Cimino’s desiderata as the main basis for our Checklist.

However, the precise meaning of the term ‘concept’ was never clearly articulated by Wüster and Cimino. In fact, four families of readings can be distinguished: the linguistic, the psychological, the epistemological, and the ontological [8]. We searched the Google Scholar digital library for the concept model from the ontological view. The applied query was ‘concept model’ AND ‘controlled medical vocabulary’. We reviewed the content of 38 available papers and selected Oliver’s GOLDMINE conceptual model [24] and the SNOMED CT concept model [23] as more comprehensive and accurate from an ontological perspective. We also searched the Google Scholar digital library for the concept model from the linguistic perspective of the terminology work. The applied query was ‘terminology work’ AND ‘concept’ AND ‘designation’. We reviewed the content of the first 20 papers out of 1530 and selected Suonuuti’s ‘Guide to Terminology’ [25] as additional criteria for the concept model.

The final list of papers selected as a basis for our work and quality methodology design are as follows:

1. Cimino’s desiderata define requirements such as content completeness, concept orientation, concept permanence, formal definition, and support for seamless terminology evolution over time [20, 4]
2. Oliver defines the GOLDMINE concept model that defines rules for concept code and name uniqueness, natural-language definition, and attribute set definition [24]
3. The SNOMED CT concept model defines the requirements for concept code and the structure of designations and properties [23, 26]
4. Suonity describes terminology work and defines the requirements for concept definition, including name, code, description, meaning, and clarity [25]

First, we highlight the rules (desiderata) given by the terminology experts that can be used to validate the quality of terminology. Not all of them may be used as rules. Cimino, for example, describes the need to maintain hierarchies and polyhierarchies. However, this requirement is a functional feature of the terminology server and cannot be applied to all types of terminology being developed. Conversely, the requirement to use identifiers without semantic meaning can be applied to most terminologies. Second, for each identified rule, we specify formal acceptance criteria and determine whether the rule can be validated automatically by the TermX terminology server or whether manual verification by a person is required. Finally, we group the criteria into three logical groups.

3. Results

3.1. Common components of terminology models

The healthcare domain's various terminology models – Common Terminology Services 2 (CTS2) [27], the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) Terminology Module [28], the Clinical Information Modelling Initiative (CIMI) [29], and CTS2-based Ontology Web Language (OWL) ontologies [2, 21, 30] – reuse similar ideas and entities, such as concepts, code systems, value sets, and concept maps. This section covers the terms used in the proposed Checklist.

A **concept** is an abstract or general idea representing a class of objects, occurrences, or phenomena. Concepts are the building blocks of a conceptual model or ontology that provide a way to categorise and understand the entities within a specific domain. A concept has unique characteristics [1], including terms, properties, relations, and associated metadata. When a concept is an abstract unit of knowledge, a word or phrase representing the concept's meaning in natural language is a term [31, 32].

Concept **designation** is a formal assignment of terms to denote a concept representation within a given domain [1]. The attributes of designation specify 1) language; 2) acceptability (preferred, acceptable); 3) use of the term (main term, synonym, or description); and 4) technical parameters, such as case sensitivity. Concept **definition** is a representation of a concept using an expression that describes it and differentiates it from related concepts [1].

Figure 1 demonstrates a concept model with a concept code, optional properties to express defined meaning, and designations [26].

Figure 1: Concept model

A **code system** is a structured collection of concepts within a specific domain [33]. Code systems often have a hierarchical or polyhierarchical structure, where codes are organised into categories or subcategories. Code systems may have different versions to accommodate updates, additions, or modifications to the set of codes and descriptors. A code system may store well-designed or simple terminologies, such as statistical classifiers.

Figure 2 demonstrates relations between a code system, concepts, and their versions and properties in the CTS2 terminology model [27]. According to CTS2, the code systems and concepts have their own versioning. A code system version is a collection of exact versions of concepts, where each concept can belong to a code system version only once.

3.2. Checklist

The terminology models enable the management of terminologies but do not define validation rules and quality criteria for terminologies. Cimino’s desiderata [13] define criteria such as content completeness, concept orientation, concept permanence, formal definition, and graceful evolution. Oliver [24] and Suonity [25] define the criteria for concept definition. The CTS2 and FHIR Terminology Module specifications provide technical and structural criteria for the code system, value set, and concept definitions [27, 28].

The idea of Checklist is to guide a terminologist in developing new terminology, reminding them of the terminology development principles and the criteria set by standards (CTS2 and FHIR). We have selected a list of

Figure 2: Fragment of CTS2 terminology model

business and technical criteria and grouped them into three blocks: a) rules that should be performed once during the design time of the code system (Table 2); b) rules applicable to every modification of the concept (Table 3); and c) rules applicable before publishing the draft version of the code system (Table 4). Every block is presented as a separate table with a rule, a description of the rule, and the acceptance criteria. The verification method indicates whether software (such as TermX) can automatically verify the acceptance criteria or whether humans must perform the verification manually.

3.2.1. Design time criteria for code systems

Table 2 summarises the design time criteria a terminologist should review and take into account before developing the content of the terminology (code system).

Table 2: Design time criteria

Rule	Type	Description
A formal methodology for content discovery and expansion is defined	Description	Formal, explicit, reproducible methods are developed and used to recognise and fill gaps in the content.
	Criteria	The methodology of adding new and changing existing concepts is specified as a narrative.
	Verification	By humans

... Table 2 continued		
Rule	Type	Description
Identification codes in code systems have no semantic meaning	Description	The code is applied to the concept automatically and does not contain the term or parent code in the hierarchy. The code may have a client namespace and checksum to support a multi-authoring process.
	Criteria	The sequence for the generation of unique numbers is created for the code system and has been rigorously applied.
	Verification	By software
The code system uses formal definitions	Description	A formal definition of a concept is precise and rigorous, using precise reasoning to remove ambiguity and provide a clear understanding of what the concept means. Usually, these definitions are expressed as a collection of relationships to other concepts in the terminology.
	Criteria	a) The properties in the code system have been defined; b) The concept definition uses properties and/or associations with other concepts in the same or external code system.
	Verification	By software
The design of a code system anticipates the evolution of medical terminology over time according to the medical knowledge evolution and needs	Description	When managing terminology, adaptability is crucial. Clear descriptions of changes are essential to understand why they occur. Good reasons for change include addition, refinement, precoordination, disambiguation, obsolescence, and minor name adjustments. Avoid detrimental changes such as redundancy, major name shifts, code reuse, and arbitrary code alterations.
	Criteria	a) Term and concept inactivation are supported; b) Ability to specify replacement concepts and reason for inactivation are supported; c) Concept reactivation is supported.
	Verification	By software

3.2.2. Criteria applied to every concept

Table 3 summarises the Checklist to ensure that the criteria themselves apply to the concepts. These criteria would be applied every time a new version of the concept is created.

Table 3: Criteria applied to every concept

Rule	Type	Description
A formal methodology for content discovery and expansion is defined	Description	Formal, explicit, reproducible methods are developed and used to recognise and fill gaps in the content of similar rigour.
	Criteria	The methodology of adding new and changing existing concepts is specified as a narrative.
	Verification	By humans

... Table 3 continued

Rule	Type	Description
Every concept has at least one designation	Description	At least one term is needed to describe the concept's meaning to human users.
	Criteria	At least one designation exists for every concept.
	Verification	By software
Every active concept has a preferred term	Description	If several terms are used to designate a concept, only one term should be selected as the preferred one.
	Criteria	Every concept may have only one designation in every language that specifies the preferred term for the concept in this language.
	Verification	By software
Each active preferred term in the terminology is unique	Description	The meanings correspond to no more than one term ('non-redundancy').
	Criteria	The uniqueness of active preferred terms of active concepts for each language are validated separately. A warning is issued if several active concepts have the same term.
	Verification	By software
Each concept in the terminology has a single, coherent meaning	Description	Concept orientation means that terms must correspond to at least one meaning ('non-vagueness') and no more than one meaning ('non-ambiguity') that corresponds to no more than one term ('non-redundancy'). A concept's meaning may vary depending on its appearance in a context.
	Criteria	If a strict rule for 'non-vagueness' and 'non-ambiguity' is impossible, a terminologist must make the decision.
	Verification	By humans
All description are concise	Description	Descriptions are as brief as possible. Carefully written descriptions contain only the information required to place the concept correctly in the concept system. Any additional information or examples are placed in a note.
	Criteria	a) A terminologist must evaluate the quality of the description manually; b) A warning will be issued if the description length exceeds the preconfigured number of symbols.
	Verification	By software. A warning may be issued by the software that issue validation by humans is needed.
The meaning of the modified concept is the same	Description	Once created, the meaning of a concept is inviolate/permanent.

... Table 3 continued		
Rule	Type	Description
	Criteria	a) In non-formal terminology, a terminologist must clearly assess the unimpaired meaning; b) In formal terminology, the meaning of existing properties should still be the same. The addition of new properties is allowed.
	Verification	By humans for non-formal and by software for formal terminologies.
The concept code and term should follow formatting conventions	Description & Criteria	Strict rules: The concept code and term should be a sequence of Unicode characters. Leading and trailing white spaces should be trimmed. Content containing double spaces is not allowed. Strings should not contain Unicode character points below 32, except for tabs, carriage return, and line feed. The code should not contain any 'grave accent' characters. Warnings: Strings should not contain tabs, newlines, or the characters @, \$, #, \.
	Verification	By software
The term must be grammatically correct	Description	Using correct grammar is essential for clarity, credibility, and perception.
	Criteria	Spell checkers do not find any errors.
	Verification	Either by software or by human. Humans can extend the dictionary of spell checkers.

3.2.3. Criteria applied to every published version

Table 4 summarises the criteria applicable to every published version. These criteria would be validated before issuing/publishing the new version of the code system. The fulfilment of these criteria should ensure the published version's uniqueness, consistency, and integrity.

Table 4: Criteria applied to every published version

Rule	Type	Description
A formal methodology for content discovery and expansion is defined	Description	Formal, explicit, reproducible methods for recognising and filling gaps in the content of similar rigour are developed and used for content discovery and expansion.
	Criteria	The methodology of adding new and changing existing concepts is specified.
	Verification	By humans
All formal definitions are unique	Description & Criteria	The collection of properties and values of one concept does not duplicate the collection of properties and values of any other concept.

... Table 4 continued		
Rule	Type	Description
	Verification	By software
The code system does not contain any terms that mean 'Not Elsewhere Classified'	Description	Terminologies should reject the use of terms that can be used to encode information not represented by any other existing terms. The problem with such terms is that they can never have a formal definition other than one of exclusion, that is, the definition can only be based on knowledge of the rest of the concepts in the terminology. The semantic meaning of these concepts will change with the addition or removal of concepts in the code system.
	Criteria	While strict rules for identifying terms meaning 'Not Elsewhere Classified' are challenging, a blacklist of frequently used words in each language can be compiled. A terminologist must then evaluate the use of terms from this blacklist.
	Verification	A warning may be issued by software; final validation by humans.
The terminology was created independently of the specific contexts in which it would be used	Description	Terminology could never be truly flexible, extensible, and comprehensive without grammar defining how it should be used. Such limitations are needed for the terminology to support operations such as predictive data entry, natural language processing, and aggregation of patient records.
	Criteria	a) The code system has context-independent concepts; b) The concepts expressed in context are specified; c) Every concept may be reused in defining another concept as a property value.
	Verification	By humans
The code system is consistent	Description	The relationships are valid and do not contain inactivated components.
	Criteria	Any active property or association (including parent concept) of the active concept should be active. If the concept is inactivated, all relationships to other concepts should be inactivated, too.
	Verification	By software

4. Discussion

Using a terminology server does not automatically ensure the high quality of the terminology created. We have identified three stages in terminology development: design, concept development, and version publication. We analysed works by Cimino [20], Oliver [24], Benson [23], and Suonuuti [25] and devised rules for each phase. Acceptance criteria for each rule were developed regarding terminology server software. The terminologist should confirm compliance with all rules during code system development. Adherence to all the rules in Checklist does not automatically guarantee the high quality of the developing code system. However, this significantly reduces the possibility of design and publication errors.

The terminology server should support multiple terminologies – well-designed terminologies and code systems designed for statistical or financial purposes [4]. Most of the developed criteria apply to well-designed

formal terminologies. Otherwise, statistical terminologies are typically non-formalised and often contain 'Not Elsewhere Classified' concepts [34]. This means that the terminology server must be flexible. For each terminology, it should be possible to configure a set of rules that apply to it. For example, checking the presence of the concept 'Not Elsewhere Classified' does not apply to most statistical terminologies.

Not only rules but also notifications must be configured in the terminology server. 'Error' and 'warning' levels should be supported at the least [35].

The terminology server must also support exception management for individual concepts. Ensuring that each preferred term is unique is a step that comes naturally to guarantee clarity in sentences or expressions. At the same time, each human language contains homographs—words spelt identically but possessing different meanings, origins, or pronunciations [36]. For example, the term 'scale' can refer to a measuring instrument, ratio, or size. For such concepts, the exception should be added to the common rule to prevent an error or warning notification after each validation.

We used the TermX terminology server and migrated hundreds of terminologies to it. The terminologies are from multiple sources in multiple countries of origin. Most migrated terminologies follow only the basic principles of terminology design and are not designed to support terminology evolution over time. Using the Checklist methodology combined with a terminology server software should significantly improve the quality of the terminology created.

5. Conclusion

This paper introduces the Checklist methodology for terminology quality assurance. It outlines validation rules, along with acceptance and verification criteria, all designed to support the development of terminology and enhance its quality. The development of high-quality terminology begins with design and concept modelling and ends with publication. The introduction of clear quality control rules and early process automation reduces the possibility of errors, allowing terminology to evolve gracefully over time and minimising maintenance costs associated with supporting terminology changes and modernisation. The proposed Checklist was implemented on the TermX terminology server and successfully verified in the Estonian Health and Welfare Information Systems Centre on several

code systems. The terminology server supports the configuration of rules for code systems due to the different purposes of the terminology.

Summary Table

What was known on the topic

1. Various health-related terminology has been developed, varying widely in quality.
2. Numerous terminology experts have formulated various rules and criteria for developing terminology.

What this study added to our knowledge

1. Rules have been categorised based on the context of use: design, publication, and concept modelling.
2. Clear quality rules and acceptance criteria have been developed to make it easier to determine whether they have been met.
3. Rules are classified according to the verification method 'software or human'. The rules verified by software were implemented and verified on the TermX terminology server.
4. The use of Checklist improves the quality of the terminology developed.

Authors' contribution

I.B. designed the idea and wrote the manuscript with support from J.M. and G.P. All authors contributed to the final version.

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Conflict of Interest

No conflicts of interest are declared.

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